

Interoperability Reference Architecture

Connecting research data services for automation and FAIR integration

Factsheet for: Developers and integrators, service providers, policymakers and funders

What is it?

The OSTrails Interoperability Reference Architecture defines how key OSTrails components, **Data Management Plans (DMPs)**, **Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs)**, **FAIR Assessment tools** and **DMP Evaluation services**, interact within research workflows.

It promotes interoperability without imposing rigid implementations, helping to avoid vendor lock-in.

The Goal

By standardising OSTrails components while allowing flexibility, the architecture enables automation, reusability, and future-proof integration not only with the services that are part of the Architecture but also with any external systems that want to exchange information with OSTrails components, across research data services and tools.

How does the Architecture work?

The Reference Architecture consists of the following conceptual components:

- **DMP Platform**, **SKG**, **FAIR Assessment Tool**, **DMP Evaluation Service**, **Data Repository**, and **other SKGs** (which can interact with each other using the SKG-IF).

Each colour (**orange**, **blue**, **green**) represents the components and communications that are subject to standardisation within each interoperability framework (IF). **Gray** represents the components and communications that are relevant for delivering the pathways, but are not subject to any of the IFs.

Contribution to EOSC

OSTrails enables federated FAIR data management across EOSC ecosystem by providing a blueprint for seamless tool integration, lifecycle-wide planning and assessment, and capacity-building through shared frameworks and pilots.

Reference Architecture explained

The Reference Architecture requires common APIs for integration with external services.

A **DMP Platform** supports the creation, management, and evaluation of machine-actionable DMPs.

Example: A researcher submits a DMP for evaluation, and the **DMP Evaluation Service** verifies its compliance with Funder requirements and returns actionable feedback. In addition, a Data Repository can enrich a dataset with missing metadata, such as the license information, based on the details described in the DMP.

An **SKG** supports the discovery and interlinking of research information related to research activities, actors, outputs such as datasets, publications, projects, funders, and organisations. Typically, this is achieved by relying on **Data Repositories** as trusted sources.

Example: An SKG queries repositories or other SKGs to enrich its graph with additional scientific metadata. Repositories and DMP Platforms then use the SKG API to retrieve this interconnected information for inclusion in DMPs.

FAIR Assessment Tools adopt the OSTRails FAIRness Reference Model, providing their outputs in a harmonised format.

Example: A DMP Evaluation Service calls a FAIR Assessment Tool to score a dataset's compliance, then returns the standardised result to the DMP Platform for display to the researcher. A Data Repository uses a FAIR Assessment Tool to evaluate the FAIRness of its data collections and identify metadata gaps.

Main capabilities enabled by the Reference Architecture

Standardised interactions:

Defines how and when components of the OSTRails architecture (DMPs, SKGs, FAIR assessment tools) communicate via APIs within Interoperability Frameworks (DMP-IF, SKG-IF, FAIR-IF).

Vendor-neutral:

Promotes interchangeable tools and services, avoiding vendor lock-in.

Supports automation:

Facilitates machine-actionable workflows for research data planning, discovery, and evaluation.

Modularity and extensibility:

Offers modular and extensible architecture that does not prescribe specific technologies, enabling diverse implementations while supporting both current and emerging research workflows, including future practices such as repositories automatically updating DMPs.

Stakeholder-driven:

Built around real-world needs and use cases from the research community.

About OSTRails

<https://ostrails.eu>

Support / Contact Us:

info-ostrails@openaire.eu

Useful Links

OSTRails GitHub: <https://github.com/OSTRails>

Documentation: <https://docs.ostrails.eu/>

Training resources: <https://ostrails.eu/training>